

MOOCS as a tool for international student recruitment: a cross-country analysis

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Abstract. One of the promises of MOOC platforms that were widely discussed during the first two waves of MOOC popularity in 2010-2016 was its marketing potential for international student recruitment. However, the research on the effects of MOOC on international enrolment is currently scarce. Based on the data from Coursera and edX platforms for MOOC supply information, and Times Higher Education World University Rankings (THE Ranking) for national and international students' statistics, this research aims to explore whether the MOOC supply is positively associated with international students enrolment. Results of regression modelling reveal that, considering the whole sample and all other factors being equal, there is no significant association between the number of MOOCs university supplies and the percentage of international students at this university. However, the second model, which includes interaction term, and thus divides the overall effect of MOOCs by different countries, demonstrates that for some countries such an association does appear. These countries are the UK, the Netherlands, Germany, and Russia. For all four countries the detected effect is positive. Finally, the study presents MOOC description page content analysis to define the elements that might promote the university enrolment and push the MOOC learners through the Marketing Funnel from Awareness and Interest to Desire and Action. This paper might be of interest for the university international affairs and student recruitment deputies, to benefit from MOOC supply the university has, or vice versa for the online learning department managers to contribute to the university key performance indicators improvement designing and redesigning online courses for the international audience.

Keywords: MOOC, international student recruitment, Marketing Funnel theory, AIDA model.

1 Introduction

Political turbulence and increased competition for talent push universities to elaborate on new tools, mostly online ones, which would allow them to preserve and increase their enrolment numbers. Massive open online courses (hereafter MOOCs) remain one of the crucial elements of the global education ecosystem, and the research shows that US and the EU university managers associate them mostly with driving student recruitment [1, 2]. Yet, surprisingly, not much empirical research is conducted to

examine the use of MOOC as a marketing tool and its impact on student enrolment [3, 4]. The professional community today attempts to reflect on 15 years MOOC history, assess MOOC initiatives and shed light on good practice and challenges. The role and achievements of MOOCs in university internationalisation strategies deserve being on agenda, as well.

The increased competition for talent, financial considerations and other numerous benefits of education export made international education marketing one of the central aspects of international student mobility [5]. Over the past decades, driven by the increased number of actors, international education marketing has adapted many instruments and business models for student recruitment. As the market grows, attracting new students becomes more challenging, which calls for more developed and personalised communication channels between institutions and prospective students.

Reputation of universities plays a significant role in students' decisions regarding their study destination. Global university rankings, while not being equal to university reputation, remain one of the ways for institutions to be visible in the global market. However, one of the critiques of the hierarchical structure of global higher education rankings is that only few institutions are visible in the rankings and those are predominantly Western universities. In these conditions, well-designed MOOCs can be a good instrument for different types of universities to show their expertise and quality of teaching for an international audience.

One of the recent trends in MOOC is the emergence of the national MOOC platforms. For example, Japan has launched its own virtual campus which provides courses in English and Japanese, as well as information about studying in Japan and learning Japanese. In 2020, China created a similar platform in cooperation with Tsinghua University, providing courses from Chinese universities in English. The Russian platform Open Education is another example of the national education platform. A recent large-scale study showed that regional MOOC providers attract larger local populations, with more inclusive demographic profiles, and might be better positioned to fulfil learners' needs [6]. These platforms aim, among other objectives, at increasing the reputation of national education systems and enhancing interest in particular study destinations among international students. However, the international MOOC platforms such as Coursera and EdX remain the largest in terms of student numbers and courses supply. Therefore they are able to reach a wider audience of potential international students.

Furthermore, the evolution of the MOOC phenomenon is under the close attention of not only educators and researchers, but also representatives of mass media, including recognised newspapers and social network sites. In that regard, MOOCs platforms can serve as channels for promotion of educational programmes and as an instrument for student outreach and recruitment. Lastly, utilising MOOCs for the mentioned above purposes goes along with the strategic university plans for increasing international visibility. Though information on MOOCs impact on university visibility is rare,

some leading universities publish the survey results showing that almost half of their MOOC learners have heard about their institution for the first time [7]. Still, having people as MOOC learners does not guarantee that they will enter the university.

Past research claims that adequate and complete information provided to students prior to enrolment is an important factor in students' decision-making regarding their study destination [8]. We argue that MOOCs can be a helpful instrument for guiding students through the stages of the decision-making, providing them with a first-hand online learning experience and familiarising with the structure, the content and quality of the selected educational programme.

To sum up, MOOCs could be a promising tool for international student recruitment. However, the evidence for that is scarce. A 2% increase has been revealed by J. Jacqmin for 72 French universities that offer MOOCs. She suggests two factors for that, which are a) institution visibility due to media buzz and Google searches around a MOOC (marginally significant but positive coefficient), and 2) direct information of MOOCs that bridge the gap between a university and potential students [9].

2 Theoretical background

The choice of study destination is a complex process. There are many social, economic, cultural, political and educational factors that affect student decisions. As there are different groups of students with different motivations to pursue study abroad, the significance of factors among different groups varies. For example, for some students the ranking of the university is the most important motivation while for others it is the tuition fees and possible career prospects. There are specific decision-making factors that depend on a university's internationalization strategy and its openness to international students. Such factors include availability of information on study options in the host institutions [10], quality of education in the institution [11], students' familiarity with the format of studies in a foreign country [12], etc. By highlighting the advantages of the university and providing helpful information on the troubling issues for prospective international students, institutions can increase their attractiveness and engage with prospective applicants in a more efficient way.

In this regard, MOOCs can be a helpful recruitment tool in multiple ways. First, it can highlight the unique courses taught at the university and the high quality of its faculty and curricula. Second, it can provide additional information on the workload and complexity of studies, and give a student an understanding of how well he/she can cope with the studies. Finally, it can give a sense of belonging and familiarity with the faculty and university community. MOOC-learners can be encouraged to enter a university campus program by special offers, such as extra-scores for a successful MOOC completion at the entrance exams or a full substitution of the entrance exams with a MOOC. It is crucial that in order for these opportunities to work, a strategic approach to using MOOC as a marketing channel is needed.

One of the fundamental theories which describes the algorithm of customer engagement (in case of this research it is seen as engagement of potential students) and provides a detailed explanation of the stages of students' decision making process is the Marketing Funnel theory [13]. The theory is based on the 4-stage model of purchase. It states that in order to make a decision for purchase, the customer goes through Awareness, Interest, Desire and Action (AIDA model) [14], where Action is the purchase of a product. Getting to know the university via MOOCs, according to the Marketing Funnel framework, is the Awareness stage; choosing this as a MOOC provider is Interest, then considering this university as a probable place for further study is Desire, and finally applying to the university is Action. While we cannot trace the last step, which is Action, we can identify call-to-action messages in the MOOCs that aim to bring students to the last stage of decision-making.

There are several factors that come into play for the AIDA model for MOOCs to work. The first factor is the level of higher education at which MOOC learners are likely to apply. MOOC learners are hardly school leavers as online learning requires highly developed self-regulated skills that high school graduates have not acquired yet [15]. In this respect, recruiting MOOC learners for Master or PhD programs seems to be a good strategic choice. In addition, the human capital index could benefit from using MOOCs for recruiting professionals for vocational education and training programs [17], especially in those countries with an underdeveloped lifelong learning system.

The second factor is the readiness of institutions to provide English-taught programs. Reports from developed and developing countries show that international learners constitute a large share of MOOC students [17, 7]. While MOOC platforms try to diversify the languages of online courses, the largest number of MOOCs and the most popular MOOCs are offered in English [18-19]. It indicates that prospective international students are proficient in English and not necessarily in the domestic languages of the universities' home countries [20]. In addition, students' decisions (particularly, when it comes to non-Anglophone students) are affected by concerns related to their success in a new study environment, workload and complexity of the international curriculum, as well as their ability to study in English, so in order for MOOC platforms to be a successful marketing instrument, universities should ensure that their web-sites and their education environment altogether signals the readiness to engage with the international audience .

The third factor is ensuring that MOOCs reflect the best teaching practices of the university. Howarth, D'Alessandro, and Johnson show that learners who have reached their course objectives for MOOCs but have broader educational goals and are satisfied with the pedagogical and delivery approach, would sooner consider the university-MOOC provider for study, then others [3]. Meanwhile, instructional quality of MOOCs is widely criticized, and research based on expert evaluations proves that is weak indeed [21]. In this respect MOOCs might provide a wrong impression of the level of instruction in the university and lead to the opposite result. Thus, it is essential that MOOCs reflect the high quality of education at the institution.

These considerations can help universities to tailor a competitive strategy for using MOOCs as an appropriate marketing instrument for attracting international students. However, available research does not allow answering the question whether MOOCs indeed are used by institutions for this purpose and whether availability of MOOCs from a specific university affects the number of international students at all.

Further research with profound analysis should shed light on whether there is such an impact, which countries and universities succeeded in unleashing MOOC potential in student recruitment, and what they do to bring people from MOOC learners into campus students. Current research is aimed at assessing MOOCs as a tool for international student recruitment for Times Higher Education Ranking universities having MOOCs on the most popular platforms (Coursera and EdX). It addresses the following research questions:

RQ 1: Is MOOC supply on an international platform associated with international students' enrolment for campus programs offered by the same university?

RQ 2: Is MOOC supply positively associated with international students' enrolment in countries with strong internationalisation strategies?

RQ3: What information about the course and university provided at the MOOC platforms can contribute to the marketing funnel for international student recruitment?

3 Methodology

3.1 Data collection

To answer the research questions, we used data from three sources: Coursera, edX, and Times Higher Education World University Rankings (THE Ranking). The data was collected by the authors via a web scraping procedure (i.e., an automatic generation and retrieval of the student/enrolment data) during the period between September and October 2021.

The first two sources, Coursera and edX, were used to retrieve data about universities' MOOCs supply. These two platforms were chosen as they are international platforms with the highest number of users and courses in the world. Thus, Coursera has 97 million learners and 6000 courses while edX has 42 million learners and more than 3500 courses.

The latter data source, the THE Ranking, contains information about a key variable for our research – the percentage of international students at university – as well as a number of indicators measuring academic and scientific performance, which were used as control variables indicating universities' reputation. We chose this ranking among others since it provides non-processed data on the percentage of international students, and this data covers a period for several years making it possible to conduct panel data analysis. In this regard, we chose the period of 2016-2021, which is the period when no significant changes in the ranking methodology have been introduced. In order to have a strongly balanced panel sample, we kept in the analysis only those universities that appear in the ranking each year throughout the mentioned period. Overall, the final sample consisted of 896 universities from 77 countries, which

resulted in 4676 observations for the subsequent analysis considering the longitudinal nature of the data.

3.2 Data analysis

To answer the research questions, we employed logistic regression analysis (regression modelling). The percentage of international students was considered a dependent variable; the number of MOOCs was used as an independent variable of interest. A set of control variables included different components of the THE ranking (more information on this is presented below), a year, and a country. The xt Stata package, devoted to longitudinal and panel data analysis, was applied to build the models.

Results of the preliminary test showed appropriateness of random and fixed-effects regression models over a pooled OLS regression model (statistics). Comparing random and fixed-effects models, we selected the random-effects model as a final one as this type of model allows us to include categorical variables into analysis (country in our case). The final models are presented in two specifications corresponding to two research questions: a main effects model for RQ1 and a model with interaction effect of number of MOOCs and country for RQ2. Both models were built with cluster-robust standard errors with university as a clustering variable.

In the THE Ranking, final universities' ranks are produced on the basis of five initial factors presented as standardized scores: Teaching, Research, Citations, International outlook, and Industry income. In regard to these factors, there are two details of data pre-processing conducted in our research that should be mentioned. First, these five factors are strongly correlated to each other with some correlation coefficients reaching 0.8 (Research and Teaching) and therefore cannot not be directly included into regression models. For that reason, these factors were transformed into three components that account for 91.5% of the initial variance using principal component analysis (PCA). Using varimax rotation, these components were extracted as uncorrelated ones in order to avoid strong multicollinearity in regression models. Factor loadings for the PCA model are presented in Appendix 1. Based on the factor loadings, the extracted components could be referred to as academic reputation, international outlook, and industry income. Second, the initial five factors are based on more detailed indicators, and a share of international students is both a part of the international outlook factor (one of the independent variables) and a dependent variable at the same time. The described problem, known as endogeneity, was solved by using one-year lagged values of all the predictors in a regression model.

Since our sample consisted of 77 different countries, some of them were grouped before using in regression models. Thus, we selected several study destinations—the largest study destinations for international students: the USA, Australia, Canada, the UK, Germany, France, the Netherlands, Russia, and China while other countries were coded as 'Other'. The choice of countries was conditioned by their leading position in terms of international student enrolment and active engagement in international student recruitment and marketing (see Table 1). In addition, the selection aims to

contain both Anglophone and non-Anglophone countries in order to provide possible insights on how MOOCs play out as an instrument for student recruitment. Detailed description of the variables used in the analysis is given in Table 2.

Table 1. International student enrolment and active engagement in international student recruitment and marketing by country.

Country	Number of International Students	Share of International Students	National strategy for international student recruitment (as of 2017)
USA	1095299	6%	No
UK	601205	25%	Yes
Canada	256455	12%	Yes
Australia	429382	29%	Yes
Netherlands	94236	12%	Yes
Germany	319902	11%	Yes
France	370052	14%	No
China	492185	1,5%	No
Russia	295263	7%	Yes

To address RQ3 a content analysis has been performed. We derived a list of universities and their MOOCs for those countries which relieved a positive association at the previous stage. Webpages presenting information about these universities and each their course pages have been manually analyzed. The search was aimed at words representing the university as international and prestigious, and inviting the MOOC learners to continue their relations with the university, enrolling for other, on-campus programs.

Table 2. Description of variables used in the analysis.

Country	Number of International Students	Share of International Students
Dependent variable	Percentage of international students	Discrete numeric variable. A percentage of international students at university, provided by the THE Ranking.
Independent variable of interest	Number of MOOCs	Discrete numeric variable. Number of courses posted by university on Coursera and edX platforms. In cases where a course belongs to several universities such a course was assigned to each of these universities.

Independent (control) variables	Academic reputation	Continuous numeric variables. The components extracted by means of principal component analysis (PCA) on the basis of the initial raw scores included in the THE Ranking: Teaching, Research, Citations, International outlook, and Industry income. Using varimax rotation, these components were extracted as uncorrelated ones in order to avoid strong multicollinearity in regression models.
	International outlook	
	Industry income	
	Year	Discrete numeric variable. The year for which all the previous statistics are considered. The variable is included in the models to take into account the common linear trend of change in percentage of international students.
	Country	A set of dummy variables corresponding to the following countries: United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, Netherlands, Germany, France, China, Russian Federation, and all other countries labelled as 'Others'. Explanation of choice of countries is provided in the text. The USA is presented as a reference category.

4 Results

4.1 Results of the regression modelling

Results of regression modelling (Table 3) reveal that, considering the whole sample and all other factors being equal, there is no significant association between the number of MOOCs university supplies and the percentage of international students at this university. However, the second model, which includes interaction terms and thus divides the overall effect of MOOCs by different countries, demonstrates that for some countries such an association does appear. These countries are the UK, the Netherlands, Germany, and Russia. For all four countries the detected effect is positive: the more MOOCs universities of these countries offer, the higher the percentage of international students in these universities is.

Table 3. Results of regression modelling

Variables	Model 1	Model 2
Year	0,91***	0,90***
Academic reputation (lagged)	1,03***	1,03***
International attractiveness (lagged)	2,44***	2,41***

Reputation at the industry (lagged)	0,90***	0,87***
Country:		
The UK	13,95***	13,86***
Canada	3,87***	3,82***
Australia	10,64***	10,64***
The Netherlands	3,1	2,96
Germany	-1,69	-1,80*
France	3,13	3,16
China	-6,56***	-6,64***
Russia	2,79	1,63
Other	-3,55***	-3,60***
Country*Number of MOOCs		
The UK		0,05**
Canada		0,01
Australia		0
The Netherlands		0,02*
Germany		0,20*
France		-0,16
China		0,02
Russia		0,17***
Other		-0,01
Constant	8,68***	8,81***
R2	0.5	0.49

4.2 Results of the course descriptions

Course-level analysis. At the course level the content analysis was aimed at spotting the course pages that contained an invitation to enrol only at this particular course (short-term strategy, one AIDA), invitation to additionally enrol to other courses offered by this university (to develop the consumer's loyalty, medium-term strategy, two or more AIDA processes, depending on the number of suggested MOOCs), and invitation to enter the on-campus programs (long-term marketing strategy, AIDA inside AIDA, enrolling a MOOC is connected to entering longer, more expensive and formal educational program).

The study showed that there are only 2,96% of course pages with an invitation for other long, on-campus programs of the university with the special offer, and all of them belong to one university, which is the Tomsk State University. The message is the following: "The certificate of completion provides extra-scores when enrolling Master programs provided by the National Research Tomsk State University. Get informed with these programs following the link <website>". 17,59% of pages

included some invitation for other online courses of the same university, which is more peculiar to courses within specialisations, but sometimes to courses united by the field, as well. 3,95% course pages had some information about the expertise of the lecturers and reputation of the university but with no call to action, such as to get acquainted with the university or the department website.

As for the topic, we suggested that MOOCs about studying language or culture of the country that these universities represent should be considered as oriented mostly for the international students. There were only 1,58% of such courses.

As soon as only universities from countries with positive association of MOOC numbers and international students share have been analysed at this stage, we suppose that their marketing approaches to international student recruitment are the most active and effective among all the MOOC producers, though this should be checked in a comparative study.

University-level analysis. In addition to analysing the descriptions of the courses, we conducted an analysis of the university profile pages at Coursera and EdX for universities from the same four selected countries: Netherlands, Germany, UK and Russia.

The results for Netherlands, Germany and Russia show some consistency: in both countries the descriptions of universities include discourses that point at the international outlook of universities and their openness to international students. These discourses include highlighting the international reputation of universities, number of partially or fully English-taught programs, mentioning the number or share of international students at the university, highlighting different study options for international students (for example, Technical University of Munich features its international campus in Singapore). Some university descriptions also include a note that completing a course gives extra points during the admission to the Master and PhD level programs at the institution.

For the UK, however, the descriptions do not contain these narratives and most of them include only a high international reputation of a university.

4.3 MOOCs for international students as the main audience.

In order to have a better understanding of the marketing potential of MOOCs, we also conducted a targeted search of MOOCs that are fully or partially designed specifically for international audiences. Using the codes “International student”, “Study abroad”, “Language learning” and “Cultural adaptation”, we found the following patterns. Only the US universities offer courses for current or prospective international students studying in the US, and there are only two courses offered by the University of Michigan (Preparing for Graduate Study in the U.S.: A course for international students) and University of Pennsylvania (Applying to the US Universities). The number of courses that provide foreign language training is significantly higher (36 courses), with English being the leading language provided mostly by the US institutions, followed by Chinese (provided by Chinese institutions) and Korean (provided by Korean universities). While the target audiences of language learning MOOCs go well beyond potential international students can be qualified as a fairly efficient marketing instrument for international student recruitment. However, the

share of courses targeting international students as the main target audience remains highly insignificant and cannot be considered an established practice.

5 Discussion

The study investigated the association between a university MOOC supply and the international students' admission for campus programs offered by the same university, as well as MOOC elements that could contribute to student recruitment. The MOOC potential for internationalisation has been widely discussed [1-2], though empirical research was scarce [3-4]. Our research showed that though there is no association in the overall sample, positive results have been received in the subsample of leading internationally attractive universities, which are the Netherlands, the UK, Germany and Russia. These universities demonstrate some efforts to attract learners' attention to them as a good option for further, formal education, such as informing them about the university reputation and faculty expertise. Direct recruitment actions, as Jacqmin J. [9] suggested, such as providing extra-scores for the entrance exams for MOOC completers, are unique.

Coming back to the AIDA theoretical model in relation to international student recruitment, we outlined that getting to know the university via MOOCs, according to the Marketing Funnel framework, is the Awareness stage; choosing this as a MOOC provider is Interest, then considering this university as a probable place for further study is Desire, and applying to the institution is Action.

The summary of the results show that while universities aim to increase Awareness of their study programs, cause Interest among international students (enrol at the MOOC course), and, in some cases, feature information that can bring students to the Desire stage (for example, mentioning the international outlook of the institution, the number of English-taught programs or the preferential conditions of admission for MOOC learners). The latter two, which are the most important stages, are generally almost not tackled. For example, universities could add links to their admissions pages, interviews with international students who currently study in the university, provide helpful guidance on application process and inform about the scholarships, upcoming webinars for prospective students and other information that can lead a MOOC learner to Action, which is applying for the university on campus programs.

Given that addressing potential international students in these ways and bringing their attention to the university as a study destination is not cost-demanding, there is a missed opportunity of using MOOCs more efficiently for international student recruitment. Thus, the discussions on the marketing potential of MOOCs for international students that took place more than a decade ago during the first wave of popularity of online learning platforms are still not reflected and not included as an intended part of a marketing strategy for most universities providing MOOCs. As MOOCs market grows and online platform learning technologies advance, universities may use this gap as a potential advantage in order to advance their

competitiveness and diversify their channels of engagement with prospective international students.

It is important to acknowledge that the second part of the research was performed with the first layer of the MOOC content only, which is the university presentation and course description pages. The MOOC course content analysis may be a promising avenue for future research. Elaborating the idea of a lagging effect of MOOC production for university internationalization, as well as the length of this lag should also be of interest for the researchers and supported with reliable methods and sufficient samples. As for methods, learner-level tracking could help to assess the conversion from MOOC participation to formal enrolment, but such a research requires consistent university databases and an access to them offered to the researchers.

The main research contribution of this paper is that our current results provide the first large-scale evidence of the association between MOOC supply and international students' admission. This finding implies several areas for university policy and strategy. First, the close collaboration of universities with MOOC platforms, particularly the joint collaboration between marketing, international and academic departments with MOOC platforms can help optimize the use of MOOCs for international student recruitment. By giving more attention on how the university appears at MOOCs platforms, universities can enhance their visibility with various strategies, such as mentioning the international outlook of the institution, the number of English-taught programs, or offering the preferential conditions of admission for MOOC learners, adding links to their admissions pages, interviews with international students who currently study in the university, provide helpful guidance on application process and inform about the scholarships, upcoming webinars for prospective students and other information that can lead a MOOC learner to Action, which is applying for the university on campus programs. Second, MOOCs can be used as a tool for international student integration and adaptation before their studies at the foreign university begins – such as the courses on academic writing and adaptation can be a good example of this strategy.

Overall, the study shows that while there is an association between MOOC supply and international students' admission, the potential of MOOCs for international student recruitment is still underexplored and can be used as a competitive advantage for universities communication and support strategies for international students.

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